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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17660774>**Modeling of a Heavy-Duty Roller Screw Actuator System and Investigation of Its Energy Consumption**Elif ERZAN TOPÇU ^{1*}¹ Bursa Uludağ University, Faculty of Engineering, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Bursa² Hid-Tek Ltd. Şti., Ar-Ge Merkezi, BursaCorresponding Author Email: crzan@uludag.edu.tr**Article Info**

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Abstract: Electro-hydraulic or electromechanical actuators are commonly used to drive high-power-density systems. Although electro-hydraulic systems continue to be widely used, especially in mobile and very high-power density applications, it has been observed that the use of electromechanical systems is increasing in industrial applications up to specific load values. In linear motion heavy-duty actuator systems, roller screw mechanisms are preferred over ball screw applications due to their high load-carrying capacities. These systems find application in various industries such as automotive, food, and aerospace and for metal cutting, pressing, robotic, CNC machining, and automation purposes. With the development of Industry 4.0, 5.0, and digital twin applications, it can be said that these types of actuators will be used more in industrial applications. In this study, we modeled an electric motor-driven heavy-duty roller screw system in the MATLAB/Simulink/Simscape environment first. We used the basic system components, such as an electric motor, gear, and roller screw mechanism, and the opposite load. We examined the closed-loop speed control of the system according to a user-defined trapezoidal speed profile. We also considered the friction force, external disturbances, and no-load torque in the modeling. Subsequently, we analyzed the system response and the effect of system parameters on energy consumption through the created model.

1. Introduction

In systems referred to as heavy-duty series, mechanical, hydraulic, and electromechanical actuator systems (EMA) are generally used for power transmission. In these systems, motion can be transmitted in two ways. Accordingly, hydraulic motors and electric motors are used for rotational motion. In contrast, hydraulic cylinders and electric motor-controlled roller screws, ball screws, acme screws, etc., are used in systems where linear motion is transmitted (Hojjat et al. 2009). Again, with these mechanisms, it is also possible to convert linear motion into rotational motion. During this energy conversion, mechanical system elements such as couplings, gearboxes, and electrical system elements such as controllers, drives, and inverters are also used. With electromechanical actuators, the desired process can be performed according to the motion and force conditions defined by the user. In recent years, EMA systems have become more advantageous than hydraulic systems up to a specific power value due to their compact structure, high efficiency, low maintenance requirements, and absence of oil leaks (Carabin, 2021; Fu et al. 2020; Lemor, 1996; Li et al., 2022; Roussel et al., 2022; Qiao et al., 2018; Topçu et al., 2024.). As it can be seen from Table 1, these screw types have some advantages and disadvantages to each other. Planetary roller screw mechanisms are a special type of screw mechanisms that utilize multiple contact surfaces for load transfer, resulting in much higher load capacity and longer service life than conventional ball screws. Basically, these roller screw systems have three types. These are the standard planetary roller screw mechanism, the inverted planetary roller screw mechanism and the multi-stage planetary roller screw (Li et al., 2022). The planetary type is widely used in industrial applications because of its inherent capacity for high accelerations and speeds, and for handling heavy loads for a long time (Lemor, 1996; Zu et al., 2018).

Table 1. Comparison of linear electromechanical actuators according to basic specifications (Anonymous, 2025a, Anonymous, 2025b)

Specification	ACME SCREW	BALL SCREW	ROLLER SCREW
Stroke Length	Medium	Long	Long
Peak speed	Medium	High	High
Max. Force	Medium	High	Very High
Accuracy	Medium	High	High
Efficiency	Low (app. %20–40)	High (app. %85–95)	High (app. %75–80)

In Figure 1 shows the basic elements and general view of a planetary roller screw mechanism. Using electromechanical actuators are extending very different sectors and areas as shown at Table 2. These systems offer a highly rigid structure, allowing precise control such as force and position. They increase repeatability and quality in assembly and forming processes. In addition, integration with servo motors enables system digitalization and Industry 4.0 compliance.

Figure 1. a) Structure of planetary roller screw mechanism. 1. Elastic retaining ring; 2. Cage; 3. Internal ring; 4. Roller; 5. Nut; 6. Screw (Chen et al., 2024), **b)** General view of roller screw system (Anonymous, 2025c)

Table 2. Industrial application areas

SECTOR	EXAMPLES FROM APPLICATION AREAS
Production and manufacturing	Pressing, broaching, sheet metal forming, assembly lines, plastic molding, automation, robotic ext.
Space and aviation	Aircraft landing gear, tube closing mechanisms, wheel steering, flight simulator, mirror control mechanism ext.
Medical	Patient beds, laboratory automation, CT scanners and MRI machines
Renewable energy	Wind turbine pitch control, solar tracker ext.

According to the results of the “Industrial Sector Final Energy Consumption Survey”, the total final energy consumption in the industrial sector in 2023 was 1706480 TJ. The “Manufacture of other non-metallic mineral products” sector had the largest share in final energy consumption by sub-sectors with 28.6%. This sector was followed by “basic metal industry” with 22.4%, “manufacture of food products” with 9.4% and “manufacture of textile products” with 7.5%. The share of the “manufacture of chemicals and chemical products” sector in final energy consumption was 7.0%, while the share of the “construction” sector was 4.4%. It was stated that electrical energy was the most consumed energy source with 475532 TJ. According to the statement made in the same source, according to the shares of energy sources in the industrial sector, electricity with 27.9%, solid fossil fuels with 24.6%, natural gas with 23.4% and petroleum products with 12.6% were the most consumed energy sources in final energy consumption (Anonymous, 2023). Therefore, considering this information, it is also important to expand the use of products that will reduce energy consumption to protect the environment and use energy economically. Özçay et al. (2023) developed an interface to calculate the consumed energy and cost of the ball-screw system driven by a servo motor according to the requested force and motion profile. Carabin et al. (2021) investigated energy

optimization of a 1-Dof mechatronic systems. In this study, we first describe the system, its elements, and its working condition. After MATLAB/Simulink/Simscape model is explained. At the last stage, we analyzed dynamic behavior and energy variations.

2. Material and Methods

The schematic view and the closed-loop block diagram of the analyzed system in this study is presented in Figure 1. Here, the user defines the trapezoidal speed profile as the desired input according to the time-speed condition using screen. In this study, the total stroke of the actuator with roller screw mechanism is 150 mm, the pressing stroke is 15 mm, and the pressing process is planned to start when the end of the stroke is close to the pressing distance. Accordingly, the forward movement approach speed was set as 50 mm/s, pressing speed as 30 mm/s, and return speed as 60 mm/s. The delay time was defined as 2 s at the end of the forward and reverse directions. Accordingly, the cycle time is calculated as 10.6 s, $\alpha=270^\circ$. The pressing force capacity of the system was determined as 55 kN, the mass of the table to be carried at the piston end was determined as 100 kg, and the roller screw and motor were selected considering these values as shown Table 3. The parameters of the components used were defined using the MATLAB/Simulink/Simscape model presented in Figure 3. A proportional (PD) type controller was used as a controller in the system, and its value was optimized using the “Check Against Reference” block. The solution was done using the “ode15s” type solver.

Figure 2. a). Schematic view, b). Closed loop scheme of the investigated system

Table 3. Basic specifications of the selected roller screw mechanism and servo motor

Specification	Value (Unit)
Product Code of rollerscrew	WPAC091-39x10
Screw shaft diameter (mm)	39
Screw pitch (mm)	10 mm
Maximum axial load (N)	55131
$C_{dynamic}$ (N)	186000
Gear ratio (-)	5
Motor maximum torque (Nm)	57.29
Motor maximum speed (rpm)	3000
Motor rated torque (Nm)	19,1
Motor rated speed (rpm)	1500

Figure 3. MATLAB/Simulink/Simscape model of the system

4. Results

The reference linear velocity-time graph, according to the velocity time values given in the "Materials and Methods" section, and the position and acceleration graph that we expect to occur according to this velocity value are shown in Figure 4a, the disturbance force variation is given in Figure 4b. Here, the linear speed profile information is given as reference input to the model.

Figure 4. a). Reference velocity-time graphic and acceleration and position variation, **b)** Disturbance forces acted on the system

When the system is operated under the effect of these inputs, the forces on the roller screw, speed and torque variations obtained at the inputs and outputs of the gear mechanism are shown in Figure 5. At the same figure, load and no-load torque variations can be also seen. As shown on the figure the torque on the motor reaches approximately 18 Nm during the forward movement in the pressing stage.

Figure 5. a) Force variations for load and roller screw, **b)** Torque variation of the system **c)** Angular speed variation of the gear input and output

Figure 6 shows velocity output response of the load. At the same figure, position and acceleration responses can also be seen. When this figure is evaluated together with Figure 4a and Figure 5c, the load follows the reference speed profile with high accuracy.

Figure 6. Output velocity-acceleration-position of load

Together with the investigation of kinematic and kinetic values on the press system, changes in power and energy according to time are also obtained. At the Figure 7, the power and energy variations is shown for different parts of the systems for one cycle. Here, the pressing process consumes the most electric power and energy as 1785 W, 868 Joule. The structural torque of

the roller screw mechanism, which occurs when there is no load, increases the power consumption in the angular motion of the motor.

Figure 7. Power and energy variation of the system

a) Power and energy on the roller screw, b) Electric motor mechanical power and energy variation c) Electrical power and energy variation

5. Conclusion

This study presents a basic dynamic modeling of an electric motor-driven roller screw actuator system usable in heavy-duty industrial systems such as presses. Firstly, according to the load and speed conditions of the system, the sizing stage is completed, and the electric motor and roller screw were selected to be used in the system from the catalogs. After the model was established in the MATLAB/Simulink/Simscape environment. The model contains an automatically tuned controller, a servo motor, a box, a roller screw, a load, and disturbance forces. A changeable trapezoidal speed reference signal was applied, and the dynamic behavior, power, and energy variation of the different parts of the system were investigated for forward and backward movements. Pressing, friction, and weight forces were also used as disturbance forces. This section was designed to be applicable to all axes. The controller parameter was optimized and applied to the controller. So, different working conditions can be investigated on this model, easily changing the working angle, load mass, friction coefficient, and other forces. It was observed that the system was following the speed profile with good agreement. Under the working conditions, the pressing operation consumed the most power and energy. No-load torque of the roller screw has an essential effect on the system and energy consumption of the screw. For future work, it can be investigated to apply different control strategies, different working scenarios, and optimization techniques to the system.

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